

Photocatalytic degradation kinetics of anti-inflammatory drug balsalazide using semiconductor TiO₂ under UV irradiation

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Abstract : Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide using titanium dioxide has been investigated in aqueous medium under UV irradiation. The rate of photocatalytic degradation of drug was monitored spectrophotometrically. The effect of different parameters like pH, concentration of balsalazide, amount of photocatalyst and electron acceptor H₂O₂ on the photocatalytic degradation process were observed. The optimization of process variables indicated that the sorption of balsalazide onto the TiO₂ was favoured at pH 10.5. Photodegradation seems to follow the Langmuir-Hinshelwood pseudo-first order kinetic model. From adsorption studies it appears that the photocatalytic degradation occurred mainly on the surface of TiO₂. It was found that photocatalytic degradation by TiO₂ is an effective, economical and faster mode of removing balsalazide from aqueous solutions.

Keywords : Photocatalytic degradation, titanium dioxide, balsalazide, kinetic study, isotherm.

Introduction

Pharmaceuticals are considered as an emerging environmental problem due to their continuous input and persistence in the aquatic ecosystem even at low concentrations. Their exposure to environment generates toxicity, mutagenicity, carcinogenicity and causes pollution, eutrophication, and perturbation in aquatic life in ecosystem¹⁻⁷. Pharmaceuticals have been detected in ground and surface water⁸⁻¹⁰, drinking water^{11,12}, tap water, ocean water, sediments and soil^{13,14}. They increase the BOD, and cause lack of dissolved oxygen to sustain aquatic life. Pharmaceuticals can also cause allergic dermatitis and skin irritation. Hence, a contamination due to pharmaceuticals is not only a severe public health concern but also may causes serious environmental problems because of their persistence. There are a lot of physical and chemical techniques such as coagulation, ozonization, membrane filtration, electrolysis, oxidation, active sludge biochemical processes, bio-degradation etc. for the removal of these types of organic contaminants from wastewater. These established technologies are often unable to reduce contaminant concentration adequately to a desired level with effectively and economically. Each of them has its own merits and demerits. Among these techniques, the

heterogeneous photocatalytic process is an authentic technique, which can be successfully used to oxidize the organic pollutants present in the aqueous system. The basic procedure behind the photocatalysis involve irradiation with suitable light energy and subsequently electron from the valence band of the titania catalyst promoted to its conduction band creating holes in valence band and electrons in conduction band. The electrons on the conduction band of the titania catalyst surface are scavenged by the molecular oxygen to produce reactive oxygen radicals, whereas the holes in the valence band become trapped by the surface bound hydroxyl radicals that are produced on oxidation of either the surface hydroxyl group and/or the surface bound water molecules. These hydroxyl radicals have very high oxidation potential, hence named advanced oxidation process (AOP), which results in the oxidation of pollutants¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Semiconductors are the key materials in photocatalytic process. Different types of semiconductors have been shown capable of promoting photocatalysis viz. as WO₃²⁰, ZnO²¹, TiO₂²² in which titania takes a role model among others. The catalyst TiO₂ is inexpensive, non-toxic, photo-chemically stable, commercially available in various crystalline forms and particle characteristics²³⁻²⁵. Titanium dioxide photocatalysis has

been suggested as a leading green technology for water purification^{26,27}. UV-irradiated TiO₂ becomes a total oxidation catalyst once in water because of the photogeneration of OH• radicals by neutralization of OH⁻ surface groups by positive photo-holes. A large variety of organics could be totally degraded and mineralized into CO₂ and harmless inorganic anions. Jain *et al.*²⁸⁻³⁰ and Mittal *et al.*³¹ have also utilized various adsorbents for the removal of pollutants from wastewater. Our laboratories are also contributing in this direction with adsorption, photocatalytic and electrochemical methods for the removal of organic pollutants from aqueous solutions³²⁻³⁴.

In the present investigation photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide using TiO₂ has been studied. Balsalazide is an anti-inflammatory drug. It is chemically (*E*)-5-[4-[(2-carboxyethyl)amino]carbonyl]phenyl]azo]-2-hydroxybenzoic acid [A]. It is particularly considered in the management of ulcerative colitis patients with troublesome nocturnal symptoms.

Results and discussion

Preliminary photocatalytic studies were carried out by taking TiO₂ containing balsalazide solution in dark. In view of the existence of several degradation pathways, the photocatalytic degradation was studied under the following experimental conditions in order to define the system completely (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide (a) in presence of all parameter viz. UV light, O₂ and TiO₂; (b) in presence of O₂ and TiO₂ but in absence of UV light; (c) in absence of TiO₂ but in presence of O₂ and UV light; (d) in presence UV light and TiO₂, but in absence of O₂ and at concentration 0.025 mg/mL, pH 10.5, temp. 30 ± 1 °C.

(a) Photocatalytic degradation of the balsalazide in presence of all parameters viz. UV light, O₂ and TiO₂.

(b) Photocatalytic degradation of the balsalazide in presence of O₂ and TiO₂ but in absence of UV light.

(c) Photocatalytic degradation of the balsalazide in absence of TiO₂ but in presence of O₂ and UV light.

(d) Photocatalytic degradation of the balsalazide in presence UV light and TiO₂, but in absence of O₂.

It was observed from the above studies that decrease in absorbance of balsalazide in absence of UV light was very slow. Presence of TiO₂ only does not catalyze the balsalazide. Only a minor loss of the balsalazide was observed on to TiO₂ surface due to initial degradation of the balsalazide on to TiO₂ surface. Minor loss was found in presence of O₂ and absence of TiO₂ while better results are observed when small amount TiO₂ is added to the solution in the presence of UV light and O₂.

Reaction kinetics : Langmuir-Hinshelwood model :

The Langmuir-Hinshelwood (LH) equation has been found an appropriate model to study the kinetic reaction rates of photocatalysis³⁵ [eq. (1)].

$$dC/dt = -k1KC/(1+KC) \quad (1)$$

where C is the bulk concentration of balsalazide in the solution, k is the reaction rate constant and K represents the equilibrium adsorption constant for a particular pollutant to the photocatalyst³⁶. Use of LH equation to describe kinetics of photocatalytic makes an assumption that adsorption of the contaminant at the TiO₂ surface is the rate limiting step. At low bulk concentration values, the LH equation becomes equivalent to a first order reaction equation.

Effect of catalyst concentration :

The concentration of TiO₂ as catalyst is one of the important parameters that influence the degradation kinetics in photocatalytic degradation process. The effect of catalyst was investigated at different concentrations of TiO₂ (0.02 g/L to 0.09 g/L). This series of experiments were performed at a constant pH (10.5) and constant concentration of balsalazide (0.025 mg/mL). The effect of catalyst concentration on the degradation is presented in Fig. 2 and it was observed that the degradation rate is increased significantly by increasing the concentration of TiO₂ up to 0.07 g/L and at 0.08 g/L there is a steep

Fig. 2. Variation of rate constants with different concentrations of TiO_2 at balsalazide concentration 0.025 mg/mL, pH 10.5, temp. 30 ± 1 °C.

increase in the degradation rate. On the other hand a further increase in catalyst loading to 0.09 g/L did not show much improvement in drug degradation and remain almost constant as shown in Fig. 2. This may be due to the fact that, in the initial stage, as the amount of semiconductor increases, the exposed surface area of the semiconductor also increases, but after this limiting value (0.08 g/L), any further increase in the amount of semiconductor does not increase the surface area and only increases the thickness of the semiconductor layer. It has been observed that 0.08 g/L of TiO_2 is optimum dose for efficient degradation of balsalazide.

Effect of drug concentrations :

Different concentrations of balsalazide (0.01 to 0.04 mg/mL) was taken to obtain the effect of drug concentration on degradation rate, and the amount of adsorbent (TiO_2) was taken constant at 0.08 g/L. It was observed that as the initial concentration of balsalazide increases, percentage degradation increases. As the initial concentration increases, more and more amount of drug was adsorbed on the surface of the photocatalyst depending on the surface provided by the catalyst. Fig. 3 exhibits the relationship of rate of the reaction of photo degradation and different concentrations of balsalazide (0.01 to 0.04 mg/mL). It is observed that the rate of degradation is slowly increased from 0.01 to 0.02 mg/mL, but after at 0.025 mg/mL there is sudden increase and become almost constant after 0.035 mg/mL.

Fig. 3. Variation of rate constant with substrate concentrations at pH 10.5, temp. 30 ± 1 °C.

Effect of pH :

Effect of initial pH on balsalazide was studied in the pH range from 6.5 to 12.5. A remarkable change was observed in the degradation of balsalazide with increase in the pH (Fig. 4). It is observed that the degradation rate increases with rise in pH of balsalazide solution. Maximum degradation of balsalazide was observed at pH 10.5 due to better solubility of balsalazide. Upto pH 10.5 the rate of degradation of balsalazide is observed constant and did not increase. Due to this response pH 10.5 is taken as optimum pH for the degradation of balsalazide.

Effect of H₂O₂ concentration :

Hydrogen peroxide is a potential additive to the photocatalytic process that also has been studied in the present investigation. Addition of H_2O_2 has resulted in different

Fig. 4. Variation of rate constant with different pH at balsalazide concentration 0.025 mg/mL, temp. 30 ± 1 °C.

results under varying experimental conditions. Hydrogen peroxide has been shown to increase the rate of mineralization of target compound balsalazide. Similar results have also been reported for other compounds³⁷. The addition of hydrogen peroxide to the heterogeneous system increases the concentration of OH• radicals since it inhibits the electron-hole recombination³⁸ and allowing an enhancement in the quantum yield of formation of hydroxyl radicals^{39,40} [eq. (2)].

Fig. 5 shows the variation of rate constants with different concentrations of H₂O₂ on the degradation of balsalazide in the solution. It has been shown that the degradation of balsalazide is increased on increasing the concentration of H₂O₂ from 0.001 mM to 0.004 mM and get constant after that. Therefore 0.004 mM has been taken as an optimum concentration of H₂O₂.

Fig. 5. Variation of rate constant with different concentrations of H₂O₂ at conc. 0.025 mg/mL, temp. 30 ± 1 °C.

Experiment with H₂O₂ was carried out in three different conditions viz.

- (i) Photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂ but absence of O₂.
- (ii) Photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and O₂.
- (iii) Photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide in presence of H₂O₂ only.

In the presence of oxygen and fixed amount of TiO₂ and H₂O₂ the degradation rate of balsalazide is reduced but the degradation is greatly enhanced in the absence of

oxygen. Maximum degradation rate is observed in presence of H₂O₂ (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide (a) in presence of H₂O₂ only; (b) in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and O₂ and (c) in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All experiments of photocatalytic degradation were conducted in a photocatalytic reactor. Irradiation was carried out using a 6 W UV lamp, placed inside the well of quartz glass photo reactor of 150 mL capacity. The reactor set up was covered with a dark black colour wooden box to prevent UV radiation leakage. All pH measurements were carried out with a decibel DB 1011 digital pH meter, fitted with a glass electrode. Degradation was studied at spectrophotometer (Systronics spectrophotometer 166, India), at λ_{max} 456 nm.

Reagents and solutions :

The anatase form of titanium dioxide with a 325 mesh, 99+ % was obtained from Sigma Aldrich and used as such without further treatment. TiO₂ was chosen due to its considerably good photocatalytic properties and be-

Scheme [A]

cause of its lower price. Balsalazide disodium [A] ($C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_6 \cdot 2Na$) with molecular weight 437.32 g/mol, was obtained from Torrent Lab Pvt. Ltd. with brand name Balacol. All reagents used were analytical reagent.

Photocatalytic degradation :

Standard solution of balsalazide was prepared in 0.1 N NaOH. Working solutions of balsalazide of different concentrations were prepared from the standard solution. Different catalyst concentration was added in 100 mL of drug solution and irradiated with UV lamp to provide energy to excite TiO_2 loading. To ensure efficient mixing of TiO_2 catalyst in the reactor, oxygen was bubbled with a constant rate from the side of the reactor continuously throughout the reaction. At a specific time interval suitable aliquots of the samples were withdrawn and analyzed after centrifugation spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 456 nm. The reaction and measurements were stopped when the balsalazide solution became completely colourless. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature (30 ± 0.1 °C).

The efficiency of degradation of balsalazide was calculated by using the following equation [eq. (3)] :

$$E (\%) = C_0 - C/C_0 \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where C_0 represents the initial concentration of balsalazide and C is the concentration of balsalazide at time t . E value indicates a higher efficiency of degradation of balsalazide onto the TiO_2 .

Conclusion

Photodegradation of the balsalazide in the presence of TiO_2 as a photocatalyst is a promising strategy. The balsalazide was oxidized or completely converted into mineral products. The degradation rate was increased significantly by increasing the concentration of TiO_2 in the drug solution. The addition of H_2O_2 is found to increase the rate of photocatalytic degradation of balsalazide. The degradation efficiency of balsalazide was best achieved with the combination of (UV + H_2O_2 + TiO_2 + O_2). Alkaline pH (10.5) of solution provides the best conditions for a better degradation of balsalazide due to increased presence of balsalazide molecules in the solution. From the results it was concluded that the photodegradation efficiency of balsalazide is 88.39%.

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